

(a) Successive Elimination (SE): Some trials fail to stop.

(b) BrakeBooster + SE: All trials successfully stop.

(c) All the plots with CDF scaled to 1000

Figure 1: Histogram of stopping times for problem instance $\mathcal{A} = \{1.0, 0.6, 0.6, 0.6\}$ (force stop after 0.1M samples). Results from 1K trials.

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Figure 2: Histogram of stopping times for problem instance $\mathcal{A} = \{1.0, 0.9, 0.9, 0.9\}$ (force stop after 1M samples). Results from 1K trials.

(a) CDF curve.

(b) Log of tail probability $\log(P(X > x))$ curve.

Figure 3: Comparison of tail distribution of FC-DSH, LUCB1, and TS-TCI. Results from 1M trials.

Figure 4: Percentages of failed trials as a function of varying δ values over the range $[10^{-5}, \dots, 10^{-1}]$. Results from 100K trials.